

EPOS
ERIC

**EPOS Data,
Data products,
Software and Services
(DDSS) Citation Guide**

EP**S**
EUROPEAN PLATE OBSERVING SYSTEM

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As adopted by the Service Coordination Committee

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1. Introduction

When using Data, Data products, Software and Services (DDSS) obtained from the EPOS Data Portal or referencing the portal itself, it is important **to provide proper attribution**, to comply with the licensing requirements and allow our team to perform an accurate **impact assessment**. Here you can find guidelines for properly citing both the *DDSS* and the *EPOS Data Portal* in different scenarios.

Proper citation provides value to your research and supports the work of your favourite data providers.

When openly sharing information about data and methodologies used in your research, you are actively supporting the establishment of **Open Science** and making a statement about your **commitment to transparency and accountability**. Thus, openness about the data used in your work is not just a matter of etiquette, nor a mere administrative task: it is a **“trust marker”**, i.e. an indicator that allows you and your research team to state that you are open to the scrutiny of peers. This helps you and your team to **establish trust not only within your scientific field, but with the public, industry, and funders**. By helping us to assess our impact you also **support EPOS’ work in bringing to you more data and services** to boost your research.

Acknowledgement of the EPOS Data Portal and the relevant data and service providers is a requirement.

By using the EPOS Data Portal you accept the [EPOS terms and conditions](#) which, among other things, require you to cite the EPOS Data Portal and the relevant datasets, data products, services and software in any publications, services, and any other derivative products.

2. How to cite Data, Data products, Software and Services (DDSS)

Whenever you publish a research output that builds upon the EPOS Data Portal, **you should always cite both the EPOS Data Portal and the specific dataset, data product, software or service, and reference their PIDs**.

Most dataset/service on the portal have a distinct persistent identifier (e.g. a DOI), which can be retrieved directly from the portal (“i” icon in the service tab) or from the metadata.

Information about the licence under which the data, product or service is offered (e.g. CC BY 4.0 International) is also available, as well as other relevant information (see Figure 1).

Here we provide recommended citation formats to be used in case of publications (scientific, commercial, generalist etc.), derivative works and redistribution of services and contents.

Please note that when a DDSS is referenced by a DOI, it comes with an extended set of metadata that complies with a well-defined schema (e.g., DataCite). Based on the available metadata, anyone may generate a bibliographic citation using the official DOI Citation Formatter tool (<https://citation.doi.org/>).

Figure 1 Licensing information for each dataset, product or service is available.

For citing the DDSS¹ in the “Acknowledgments” of any publication

This [study/project/research] used the EPOS Data Portal (<https://www.epos-eu.org/dataportal>) to access [DDSS name] provided by [insert DDSS provider(s)]. [insert relevant DOIs/PIDs if available]. Accessed on [DD-MM-YYYY].

For citing the DDSS¹ as a reference in any publication

For DDSS having a DOI:

Use the preferred bibliographic standard to generate a citation using the DOI Citation Formatter (<https://citation.doi.org/>) and add the following:

Accessed on [DD-MM-YYYY] through the EPOS Data Portal(<https://www.epos-eu.org/dataportal>).

For DDSS NOT having a DOI:

[Insert DDSS name] [insert version if applicable], provided by [insert DDSS provider(s)], [insert licence information if applicable], [insert relevant DOIs/PIDs if available]. Accessed on [DD-MM-YYYY] through the EPOS Data Portal (<https://www.epos-eu.org/dataportal>).

For citing the EPOS Data Portal as a reference in any publication

Bailo, D., Paciello, R., Michalek, J. *et al.* The EPOS multi-disciplinary Data Portal for integrated access to solid Earth science datasets. *Sci Data* 10, 784 (2023). <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41597-023-02697-9>

For citing the EPOS Data Portal and DDSS¹ in derivative works

This [product/service] was generated using the EPOS Data Portal (<https://www.epos-eu.org/dataportal>) to access [DDSS name] provided by [insert DDSS provider(s)]. [insert relevant DOIs/PIDs if available]. Accessed on [DD-MM-YYYY].

For citing EPOS Data Portal contents different from DDSS¹ (e.g. images, pictures)

Credits: EPOS Data Portal (<https://www.epos-eu.org/dataportal>), [insert provider], [insert author if available], [insert licence information if applicable], [insert relevant DOIs/PIDs if available]. Accessed on [DD-MM-YYYY].

¹ DDSS = Data, Data Products, Software, Services

3. Machine-readable citation files

The general EPOS Data Portal Citation file in .cff format is available in Appendix 1. Machine-readable versions for citing specific element (e.g. software, dataset, etc), will be made available on the EPOS Data Portal.

4. Further inquiries and contacts

Should you have any questions regarding how to reference the EPOS Data Portal or one of its services or components please contact communication@epos-eric.eu.

Please let us know about your work and results with the EPOS Data Portal! Whenever you publish an article, or any other data product or service that builds upon EPOS data and services, please notify us at communication@epos-eric.eu. We are always on the lookout for a good scientific use case, and we will be happy to help in making your work visible!

Appendix 1

EPOS Data Portal machine-readable citation

This CITATION.cff file was generated with cffinit.
Visit <https://bit.ly/cffinit> to generate yours today!

cff-version: 1.2.0

title: EPOS Data Portal

message: >-

When using data, data products, software and services (DDSS) obtained from the EPOS Data Portal or referencing the portal itself, it is important to provide proper attribution, to comply with the licensing requirements and allow our team to perform an accurate impact assessment. Further information on the EPOS Data Portal citation guidelines can be found at: <https://www.epos-eu.org/dataportal>

type: dataset

authors:

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website: '<https://www.epos-eu.org/>'

repository-code: '<https://github.com/epos-eu/data-portal>'

url: '<https://github.com/epos-eu>'

abstract: >-

The European Plate Observing System (EPOS) is a long-term initiative aimed at integrating research infrastructures for solid Earth science in Europe. EPOS provides a sustainable, multidisciplinary user-oriented platform - the EPOS Data Portal - that facilitates data integration, access, use, and re-use, while adhering to the FAIR principles.

keywords:

- EPOS Data Portal

- Solid Earth Science

- geospatial data

- spatial visualization

- data interoperability

- multidisciplinary resources

license: GPL-3.0

version: 1.0.1

date-released: '2023-12-07'

